

DR.B.R AMBEDKAR'S VIEW ON EDUCATION FOR DALITS: A HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE**Ms. Pradnya B Gudhe,***Research Scholar, S.M.D.L. College,
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Guided By:

Dr. S C Lahupachang,*Principal, SMDL College,
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The objective of this research paper is to look into Dr.B.R.Ambedkar's views on Education for Dalit's. Dr. Ambedkar's recognized that education was the indispensable prerequisite for the rebuilding of the society on the principles of equality and justice. Reviewing the progress of education in Indian society he found that during the pre-British and later for many years right to education was limited to higher castes. He started a protest for the education to be provided to the Dalit boys and girls without discrimination. Dr. Ambedkar put forwards his views during the budget session and said, Education is something which must to be carried within the grasp of one and all. He said, education should to be cheapened in all likely ways. Participating in the session of Bombay University Act and Primary Education Amendment Bill, he put forth his opinions in bringing reforms in Education. Later he established the People's Education society, and initiated colleges at Bombay and Aurangabad respectively. By this he started a momentum for making education come under the accessibility of masses.

Introduction:

Dr. B R Ambedkar said "Education is the most important weapon to cut the social slavery and it is the education which will enlighten the downtrodden masses to come up and gain social status, economic betterment and political freedom". Though several efforts were made by Dr Ambedkar to establish an equalitarian society in India, still his vision is not fully realized due to various obvious reasons. Dr Ambedkar made an attempt to achieve this objective through his educational project, which is the part of my research paper.

OBJECTIVES:

1. To Assess the Contributions of Dr. B.R. Ambedkar in the field of Education.
2. To explore the Changes in life of downtrodden section through Dr. B.R.Ambedkars Contribution to field of Education.

METHODOLOGY:

The study was conducted by primary and secondary sources through historical, analytic approaches. Method consists of analysis concepts and arguments, blending of ideas and evidence drawn from different sources.

IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATION:

Dr.B.R.Ambedkar knew that education was the necessary precondition for the reconstruction of the society on the principles of equality and social justice. Studying the development of education in Indian Society he found that during the earlier period of British Raj, right to education was restricted to higher castes. He fought for the education of masses without discrimination of caste and sex. He said, “Education is something which ought to be brought within the reach of everyone. Taking active part in the discussion on Bombay University Act and Primary Education Amendment Bill, he contributed his views in bringing reforms in Education.

He founded the people’s Education society, and started colleges at Bombay and Aurangabad. He repeatedly discussed with government that providing equal educational opportunities to all without discrimination. The people belonging to low castes i.e. the scheduled castes were denied all privileges and facilities, including educational facilities. They were so poor that they could never think of sending their children to educational institutions. Educationally therefore, they were extremely backward.

Dr.B.R.Ambedkar believed that education would greatly contribute to the improvement of the untouchables. He always encouraged his followers to reach excellence in the field of knowledge. Education makes man enlightened, makes him aware of this self–respect and also helps him to lead a better life materially. One of the causes of the degradation of the untouchables was that they were denied the right to education.

In order to promote education among untouchables Dr.B.R.Ambedkar set up hostels for untouchable students at different places like Panvel, Pune, Nasik, Sholapur, Thane and Dharwad with donations and grant from district and local authorities. Dr.B.R.Ambedkar wanted to set up separate institutions for the untouchables. He established the People’s Education Society in July 1945.

With the constant struggle of Dr.B.R.Ambedkar some progress has taken place. But due to some reasons education and literacy among the people belonging to downtrodden is still very low. Much attention is already being paid, but distance to be covered is very long. The government is giving scholarships to the downtrodden students. They are encouraged to go abroad for higher studies. Admission provisions to professional and non-professional courses are put into board. Separate girl hostels have been opened for them. Book banks scheme have been started and many problems which stand on the way of non-utilisation of educational facilities by them are slowly removed.

CONCLUSION:

Dr B R Ambedkar has included Article 45 in the Directive Principles of State Policy that, “the state shall provide, within a period of ten years from the beginning of this Constitution, for free and compulsory education for all children until they complete the age of fourteen years.” The government of India has passed the bill of Right to Education Act 2008 and paid a great tribute to the contributions of Dr B. R. Ambedkar to mass education. The policy of the Government of India of providing basic education is focusing particularly on side-lined groups, poorer sections and the girl child. There are several problems to fulfil Dr. Ambedkar’s vision of providing education to all. There is urgent need to

make such policies into reality starting from the primary level to the higher education in Urban India and Rural Bharat that help to realize the vision of Dr B R Ambedkar.

SUGGESTIONS:

To overcome the problem of education for downtrodden it may be suggested that the authorities should take proper steps to provide facilities for effective participation of downtrodden population in education.

Adult education should be encouraged to motivate the parents or guardian regarding education.

Some type of counselling and guidance should be arranged for the parents to make them aware about the importance of education in their life. The traditional occupation has to be redeveloped with modern techniques. In educational institutions employment courses should be opened in such occupation. The field work and Government survey should be done properly and special arrangements should be made for large publicity among the dalit people about different schemes of development and the ways and means to improve their status and participating in such schemes. The provision made in the constitution for the upliftment of the dalit people to be given publicity through mass media like radio, television, newspapers and wall posters.

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